

Relative-pose Optimisation for Robust and Nonlinear Control of Unmanned Aerial Manipulators

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Abstract—Recently, the complexity of control systems for autonomous Aerial Manipulators (AMs), i.e. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) + Robot Manipulator (RM), is growing faster as per our demand of being able to perform more and more complex tasks. In the present work, we go a step forward adding an optimiser to the actual (nonlinear) control strategy, in order to comply with high-level control demands related to safety, accuracy and efficiency of the operational task. The actual strategy combined robust controllers with separate references—for both aerial vehicle and robot manipulator—optimising their shared priorities. Here, we demand the controller to meet an additional feed-forward action, so that the *a priori* free degree of freedom of the UAV relative-pose reference is optimised in real time according to the aforementioned requirements. In particular, the influence of the UAV relative-pose reference on the capabilities of the AM has been thoroughly analysed, demonstrating among others the benefits of a correct configuration to meet such high-level requirements, while reducing the End-Effector (EE) error, preventing unstability of hazardous situations and increasing the energetic efficiency of the whole system. A complete analysis of realistic simulations on a benchmark AM is reported.

I. INTRODUCTION

Aerial robotic manipulation has emerged in the last years thanks to the progress in mechatronics, control systems and perception and planning systems. The broad application possibilities include contact inspection, maintenance, and assembling at inaccessible places. Some examples of different AMs with multi-joint arms have been presented in [1], [2] and [3]. For a detailed literature review on platforms and control systems of UAVs and RMs we refer interested readers to recent author's work and references therein in [4], [5] and [6]. In fact, interaction capabilities have been demonstrated under the cutting-edge framework provided by ARCAS project [7]. The complexity of the available AM is currently being increased in the AEROARMS project [8] that is funding this work.

From a control point of view, three different strategies can be adopted to control AMs in free flying: i) control by means of a full integrated model with all the degrees of freedom of the aerial platform and the manipulator, as in [9] and [10]. ii) decentralised control of the subsystems, as for example the control of the aerial vehicle taking into account the joint angles of the RM [11], or an optimised interconnection criteria as in [6]; and iii) decoupled control of each subsystem by cancelling each other effect out, as in [12] by means of the application of impedance control.

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This work continues the research line followed by the authors. First, a robust and nonlinear controller for a simplified AM based on Passivity-based control was reported in [4], ensuring that the UAV is endowed with disturbance rejection capabilities. Secondly, even though the well-known CLIK algorithms provide good performances, the outdoor aerial manipulation is specially challenging for the control system and additional robustness properties have been essential to cope with random EE position deviations during operations, so that in [5] those algorithms were improved with the benefits of an integral action. Finally, in [6] an optimiser was included in the control loop to coordinate subordinate tasks between both *a priori* decentralised controllers.

Fig. 1. Optimisation problem: example of safe (check-mark) and unsafe (cross-mark) relative-poses.

All together are a sine qua non requirement for the present work. Let us explain the idea with the help of Fig. 1. For a fixed target position of the EE there are many possibilities (infinity in theory) to place the UAV with respect to the RM, this is what we call the extra degree of freedom in the UAV reference position, that it was just fixed in previous works. In Fig. 1 the check mark position clearly is safer than the cross one, which would demand a high thrust—possibly up to the saturation limit—to counteract the torque transmitted by the RM to the UAV, making the whole AM collapse. The way that we include this in the controller strategy is running another optimisation algorithm on the relative pose and feeding it forward the information to the UAV controller, so that it is acting like an automated decision maker. The main difference with previous works is that, while in [6] both UAV and RM references were independent, here the UAV reference is dependant on the flight conditions and relative to the EE reference. The decision maker optimisation criterion accounts for accuracy, safety, efficiency and energy consumption of the operation. To this end, first a thorough analysis of different configurations of the UAV reference position depending on the EE target position is performed. Secondly, the possible influence of disturbances and wind are

considered, obtaining a set of different optimal configurations depending on the external conditions that the AM is facing at a certain moment. All that information is collected to construct an optimisation map which is included in realistic and successful simulations.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II describes briefly the framework and the control strategy; in Section III the simulation model is described; Section IV is devoted to the numerical analysis to obtain a cost-functional map for optimisation; and in Section V realistic simulation results are presented and finally a conclusion section.

Notation: All vectors are *column* vectors. When clear from the context the subindex of the operator ∇ and the arguments of the functions will be omitted. The form $\|\cdot\|_{\Gamma}$ denotes the Euclidean norm weighted by a positive definite matrix Γ .

II. CONTEXTUALISATION AND BACKGROUND

The dynamics of AMs can be described by means of the Lagrange equations [13], [14] which denoting by $(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$ the generalised coordinates become

$$\Sigma(\ddot{q}, \dot{q}, q) = u + u_{ext}, \quad (1)$$

where it is well-known that $\Sigma(\ddot{q}, \dot{q}, q)$ collects the inertial, potential and centrifugal and Coriolis terms, u_{ext} models the non-potential external forces, as friction and drag, and $u \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the input vector, e.g. for a quadrotor-like AM

$$u = G(q) \cdot F, \text{ with } G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}, m := 4 + N,$$

and $F = [T, \tau]^T$, with $T \in \mathbb{R}^4$ the thrusts of UAV and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^N$ the joint torques of the RM. Alternatively, the whole system can be described in a Cartesian space, resulting in an equivalent formulation to (1) using the analytic Jacobian matrix $J(q)$ [15], wherever away from singularities.

As it has been thoroughly discussed in [4], the closed-loop stability analysis becomes very involved due to the mechanical underactuation of UAVs (see [16], [17]) and hence of AM dynamics. Indeed, this added complexity requires an extensive analysis of both free $u_{ext} = 0$ and constrained motion $u_{ext} \neq 0$ cases, not being able to follow arbitrary commanded trajectories. Additionally, it is worth to remark that, as long as the potential energy of UAVs is lower unbounded [4] providing to AMs with a cyclo-passivity property, i.e. not having stable equilibria whenever the propulsive system is at idle.

In what follows in this section we summarise the nonlinear control strategy designed for AMs and we refer interested readers to [6] and [4], [5] for further details¹. As in [6], let us use the sketch of Fig. 2 to describe the whole control strategy, with the novelty here of the decision maker Φ :

- 1) The interconnection criterion between the UAV and the RM dynamics is described by the torque transmitted from the RM to the UAV, namely τ_d .
- 2) The UAV controller takes into account that interconnection torque τ_d while robust to its uncertainty.

¹Unlike in [6], in here we avoid the term multi-task to prevent confusion with path planning approaches.

- 3) The optimiser, represented by its cost functional Ψ , adapts the demanded torque τ_d to yield τ^* according to the interconnection criterion.
- 4) The mission RM controller tracks the request τ^* .
- 5) The control loop is closed with the actual value of the dynamically-coupled torque transmitted to the vehicle from the RM, with a mismatch $\tilde{\tau}$ over the demand.

The novelty, w.r.t. [6], is the local optimiser, so called decision maker, characterised by the cost functional Φ (see Fig. 2), that receives information of the EE position and orientation and—under some prescribed criteria—provides optimised UAV references.

Fig. 2. AM control strategy.

Remark 1: The above control strategy demands, on the one hand the UAV control algorithm requires disturbance rejection capabilities to cope with the reduced-order model and more importantly with the mismatch between τ_d and $\tilde{\tau}$; on the other hand, the RM control algorithm needs good tracking capabilities to “catch up” with torque τ^* and low sensitivity to numerical errors. In the meantime, it is crucial to define the optimiser via bounded mathematical operators suitable for being computed in finite time. Finally, the local optimiser can be seen as a feedforward-like action on the UAV references.

Let us describe succinctly each part of the controller to contextualise and introduce the new development.

UAV. A controller has already been reported in [4] and references therein, for a simplified version of the available experimental platform. It is based on the Passivity-Based Control methodology IDA-PBC which—upon solving some Partial Differential Equations²—provides a generalised port-controlled Hamiltonian structure in closed loop with a state-state feedback of the form $F = \hat{F}(q, \dot{q})$. By construction an energy-like Lyapunov function is provided ensuring the equilibrium $(q_*, 0)$ of the closed-loop dynamics is stable, and asymptotically stable if it is locally detectable from its output.

RM. A robust version of the CLIK algorithm has been already used in [5] and [6] and references therein. The absence of structured spaces in outdoor

²See [4], [18] and references therein for details.

aerial manipulation is very challenging for the control strategy and hence, the added robustness, via integral action, is essential to deal with arbitrary cartesian EE trajectories and to execute smart manipulation outdoor tasks. It is also worth mentioning that in [6] some other ad-ons to improve accuracy and robustness were included. Recall that these algorithms for redundant manipulators can be solved as a locally-constrained optimisation. Thus, if \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{l} be the joint space and Cartesian task space dimensions, respectively, then for a given Cartesian velocity $v \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{l}}$ and a Jacobian $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{l} \times \mathcal{N}}$ we look for a joint velocity $\dot{\gamma} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N}}$ that solves a optimisation problem defined through a cost functional $\Psi_{core}(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}, \ddot{\gamma})$.

AM- Ψ . Aforementioned controllers for UAV and RM have been designed separately considering their operations as disturbances to each other. In [6] authors progressed interconnecting both algorithms through shared subordinate tasks by means of an nonlinear optimiser. The optimisation criteria thereby presented have been included by means of a redesigned cost functional to fulfil the desired torque τ_d interconnection requirement, resulting in

$$\Psi_{add}(\gamma, \dot{\gamma}, \ddot{\gamma}) := \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_{ID} \|\dot{\hat{\gamma}}\|_{\tilde{W}}^2 + \alpha_{\tau_d} \rho(\tilde{\tau}))$$

that represents the added term to the original optimisation criteria Ψ_{core} , i.e. $\Psi := \Psi_{core} + \Psi_{add}$, to reduce the torque discrepancy $\tilde{\tau} := \tau_d - \tau^*$ with function $\rho \in \mathbb{R}_+$, constants $\alpha_{ID}, \alpha_{\tau_d} \in [0, 1]$ and weighting matrix \tilde{W} . An extensive simulation analysis to test the whole nonlinear strategy was performed in [6], and the stability properties of the whole nonlinear control strategy will be reported elsewhere [19].

AM- Φ . The novelty introduced in this work is another optimisation algorithm—in a higher level in the control hierarchy—so that we can take the advantages of the extra degree of freedom of the UAV placement and with cost functional denoted by Φ (see Fig. 2). As it has been aforementioned, we could say that this optimiser acts as an UAV reference decision maker (keep in mind Fig. 1). The full block diagram of the control system is provided in Fig. 3, where we underscore the main difference w.r.t. its companion in [6]. In this work, the UAV references are dependant on the EE target position for a successful automated operation. Thus, in order to analyse the influence of the UAV references on the RM capabilities, several parameters have been chosen to optimise, in a way, the operation of the AM. In particular, such optimisation is based on accuracy, safety and efficiency of such operation, and the parameters to characterise the interconnection are: the position and orientation RMSs, the link torque RMS and the energy consumption of the operation.

Fig. 3. Full block diagram of the control system.

III. BENCHMARK APPLICATION

In order to analyse the UAV references optimiser and compare with the control strategy in [6], the simulations are based on a longitudinal dynamics model of an AM, comprised by an UAV plus a 5-link planar RM (Fig. 4), whose characteristic parameters are presented in Table I. The generalised

Fig. 4. Benchmark AM sketch.

coordinates of the AM from (1) are $q = (\xi, \gamma)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^5$, i.e. $n = 8$ and $\mathcal{N} = 5$, with $\xi = (x, y, \theta_0)^\top$ and $\gamma = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4, \theta_5)^\top$ being the position of the UAV and RM configuration, respectively (see also [15] and [20]). The

TABLE I
MODEL PARAMETERS

Masses[kg]		Lengths[m]			Inertias[kg · m ²]	
m_{UAV}	m	l_T	l	d	I_{UAV}	I_L
8	0.1	0.5	0.15	0.1	$8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-4}$

UAV parameters according to [6] are $m_B = 5m$, $m_Q = m_{UAV}$, and $I_{22} = M_{33}^{RM}(q)$. The inertia matrix of the Aerial Manipulator is formed by those of the vehicle and the Robot Manipulator, $M(q) = M^{UAV} + M^{RM}$, assembled through their elemental Jacobians associated with translations and revolutions, subindexes t and r respectively

$$M^{UAV} = m_{UAV} \left(J_t^Q \right)^\top J_t^Q + I_{UAV} \left(J_r^Q \right)^\top J_r^Q$$

$$M^{RM}(q) = m \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(J_t^i(q) \right)^\top J_t^i(q) + I_L \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(J_r^i \right)^\top J_r^i$$

Notice that both M^{UAV} and $M^{RM,r}$ are matrices of constant terms, resulting in simplified Coriolis matrix where Christoffel symbols read

$$c_{ijk} = \frac{m}{2} \left(M_{ij,k}^{RM,t} + M_{ik,j}^{RM,t} - M_{jk,i}^{RM,t} \right),$$

with $M_{ij,1}^t; M_{ij,2}^t; M_{11,k}^t; M_{12,k}^t; M_{22,k}^t; M_{88,k}^t$ zero $\forall i, j, k$.

To interconnect both platform and manipulator controllers it is considered imperative to accurately appraise the link torque transferred by the RM to the UAV in order to minimise the discrepancies between the real value and the demanded one. A first estimate is obtained using a similar idea to the one used in structural sub-matrices static reduction [21], considering the dynamic equations without the friction and the drag terms (1). Thus, neglecting translational coupling terms the approximation for this torque becomes

$$\tau^* = M_{0\gamma}(\gamma)\ddot{\gamma} + M_{\xi\gamma}\ddot{\xi} + \frac{1}{2}\|\dot{\gamma}\|_{C_{0\gamma}^2(\gamma)}^2 + \nabla_{\theta_0} V$$

where $C_{0\gamma}^2(\gamma) = 2c_{3ij}$ for $i, j = 4, \dots, 8$, resulting in a significant reduction of the computational load.

Remark 2: We underscore that to improve the realism of the simulations the rotors of the UAV have been saturated and filtered to avoid extreme thrusts; a low-pass filter imitates the first order behaviour of the rotor dynamics in both delay and vibration filtering aspects; and the UAV dynamics have been enriched with an CFD-based aerodynamic model.

IV. NUMERICAL CHARACTERISATION OF THE OPTIMISATION CRITERIA

In this section, a thorough analysis via extensive simulations is performed with a twofold objective: first, to be able to characterise the functional maps of the criteria adopted and, second to construct the optimisation mapping merging all the information gathered in those simulations.

Thus, considering the vertical symmetry of the problem and the hazardous capture conditions above the plane of the rotors, the characteristic parameters have been calculated in the following EE reachable region: a sector (from 15° to 90°) of a circular ring centered in the EE target from the 30% to the 90% of the total maximum length of the manipulator, L_{RM} , which has been meshed as presented in Table II. This area represents the expectedly acceptable configurations of the UAV with respect to the EE target, including options, such a long-range capture, that may not be the most recommendable a priori. In a preliminary analysis,

TABLE II

UAV REFERENCE SIMULATION MESH IN POLAR COORDINATES

Angular coordinate mesh	$15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 90^\circ$
Radial coordinate mesh	$30\%, 50\%, 70\%, 90\%$ of L_{RM}

the problem has been studied in ideal unperturbed conditions in order to obtain early information of the influence of the parameters. However, uniform wind conditions and white noise have been considered in the final simulations to study the influence of such disturbances on the optimal configuration and the presence of infeasible configurations for certain conditions. Finally, these four parameters have been integrated in normalised optimisation cost functional maps to determine recommendable configurations of the UAV reference towards the EE target depending on the flight conditions and possible obstacles.

A. Preliminary analysis in ideal conditions

As above mentioned, in this first analysis of the parameters the AM has been considered to fly in a non-perturbed fluid field and the signal noise has not been included in the group of reduced 30 s simulations. Under this circumstances, a set of results have been obtained to determine the characteristics of these main parameters, resulting in the normalised group of maps shown in Fig. 5, where $D_{ref} = 1$ cm, $\alpha_{ref} = 5^\circ$ and $M_{ref} = 0.5$ N · m. For each one of the

Fig. 5. Normalised parameter maps for the preliminary optimisation criterion: (A) Energy consumption to reach the EE target; (B) Final distance RMSE; (C) Final orientation RMSE, and (D) Permanent link torque RMSE.

four parameters, the recommendable configurations of the UAV reference position towards the EE target have been highlighted in green, corresponding deep green areas to highly recommendable configurations and lighter green ones to alternative solutions in case the most beneficial are not possible. Moreover, the non-recommendable configurations for each parameter are shown in red (unsuccessful operation) and orange (non-recommendable), generally corresponding to far range capture attempts and nearly vertical or horizontal relative positions of both references. However, this set of maps show that the different recommendable zones for each parameter usually are overlapped with non-recommendable or even unsuccessful ones. All together it leads to an essential trade-off between them to determine acceptable solutions.

Fig. 7. Final normalised optimisation cost functional map, where the contour lines correspond to the following levels: 0.12, 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6.

Fig. 6. Preliminary normalised optimisation trade-off cost functional map in ideal conditions.

Taking this overlap condition into account, a preliminary weighted optimisation criterion map is presented in Fig. 6, giving priority to the position error ($\alpha_{dist} = 0.65$) and the energy consumption ($\alpha_{cons} = 0.2$). However, the orientation ($\alpha_{orient} = 0.1$) and link torque ($\alpha_{torque} = 0.05$) errors have also been considered in order to modify the proposed solution in case it produces dangerous conditions. As expected, the recommended configurations correspond to the 45° to 90° sector, having a badly conditioned area in 90° for distances between 60% to 85% of the manipulator total distance.

B. Analysis in realistic conditions

In a second set of simulations, the effects of both uniform wind and white noise disturbances have been considered and their duration has been extended to the 45 s. For five different representative wind conditions, $(V_w)_y = -10, -5, 0, 1, 2$ m/s (positive winds correspond to tailwind, while negative ones represent headwind conditions), the four characteristic parameters have been obtained. These sets of simulations have resulted in a group of maps similar to Fig. 5, whose

analysis have been used to calculate the different normalised optimisation cost functionals for each wind condition (Fig. 7) using the same weights of the preliminary criterion map. The different maps show that the recommendable configurations clearly vary with the wind conditions, being advisable to choose nearly vertical solutions for strong headwind conditions while avoiding this setting in other cases. Moreover, the horizontal far-range configurations should not be used in any case, as long as they have been proved to result in unsuccessful operations.

Furthermore, close-range solutions have shown to be acceptable under disturbances in the range of wind speed studied and should be considered suitable in case the operation hold under inaccurate estimated wind conditions. This outcome is specially interesting compared to the unperturbed preliminary analysis (Fig. 6), where this zone was considered as alternative in case a better solution was not possible.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning that the results for each wind condition have been estimated using fifth-degree polynomial functions in Cartesian coordinates, leading to an easily optimised approximated cost functional taking into account the influence of uniform wind conditions.

TABLE III
OPTIMAL SOLUTION PARAMETER RESULTS

V [m/s]	-10	-5	0	1	2
Consumption [J]	4887	5225	7256	4997	5389
Distance RMSE [mm]	4.8	2.7	3.3	4.0	3.6
Orientation RMSE [$^\circ$]	2.78	1.97	3.39	2.33	1.83
L. torque RMSE [N·m]	0.64	1.16	1.16	1.41	1.11

Using this solution, the optimal configurations for the five studied cases has been computed and the results are collected in Table III. As expected, the optimal solution energy consumptions are moderate in comparison with larger values simulations of up to 20 kJ. In contrast, the inefficiency peak for the consumption with no wind could seem surprising, but it is produced by a slower capture operation in comparison to the tailwind (favoured by an initial force towards the target) and headwind (abruptly slowed down close just before the capture) approaches. It is also worth mentioning the small

link torque error for the -10 m/s wind condition, produced by the compensation of the negative UAV torque demand to counteract the drag forces with the RM link torque in this configuration. Finally, the outstanding distance RMSE results in the wide range of wind conditions simulated evince the benefits this solution could render in real application.

V. CLOSED-LOOP IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 8. Variable UAV reference approach, with EE trajectory in blue and UAV one in red. Detailed plot highlights the recommended UAV references during the whole operation.

Subsequently, this optimisation criterion has been used in a closed-loop demonstrative simulation shown in Fig. 8, where a horizontal sinusoidal wind (with an amplitude of 3.75 m/s , a bias of -2.25 m/s and a frequency of 0.05 Hz) has been introduced. This simulation is used to compare the performance with the static reference option and analyse the reconfiguration of the AM produced by the optimisation algorithm (Fig. 9). It is worth mentioning that although

Fig. 9. Reconfiguration of the AM under wind disturbances via the optimiser Φ change of UAV reference.

having static references, the UAV controller leaves partially unattended its target if necessary, as can be seen in (B) of Fig 10, as well as it introduces a steady-state error in both of the situations in order to prioritise the operation of the

Fig. 10. UAV variable reference solution (in blue) compared with a constant reference one (in red): (A) Vertical position of the UAV (references dotted); (B) Horizontal position of the UAV (references dotted); (C) Norm of the position error of the EE.

manipulator. However, the most important result is the clear reduction (of about a third on average) of the position error produced by the proposed solution in (C). Even though this parameter has not been the only one chosen to characterise the different configurations—as long as it is the only one essential to complete a successful operation—it is considered the most representative to demonstrate the improvement of the proposed solution.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the influence of the UAV reference position on the capabilities of the AM with a nonlinear control strategy under disturbances has been thoroughly analysed, demonstrating the important benefits of a correct relative pose in the feasibility, accuracy, efficiency and safety of the operation. It is shown that a simulation-based configuration choice reduces the position and orientation error, as well as it prevents the destabilisation of the AM and increases the energetic efficiency of the whole mission.

Moreover, the optimisation of this relative pose allows the use of the additional degree of freedom available, i.e. UAV reference, to take into account external conditions directly and detect hazardous situations in future work. Unacceptable configurations in the region considered, influenced by external factors (such as obstacles), could be easily detected beforehand and hence avoided.

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